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Hands-on Experiments vs. Computer-based Simulations in Energy Storage Laboratories

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ABSTRACT

This cross-over study compares student laboratory work conducted in two different learning modes: first as a practical hands-on exercise and second using computer-based simulations. The research methodology was optimized to avoid other effects on the learning outcome. To evaluate the influence of the mode, short tests on knowledge gained during the previous experiment were conducted at the beginning of the next laboratory session. In 2016, forty students have taken part. Overall learning results of hands-on experiments were slightly better than those of simulated laboratories, but the difference in performance was not statistically significant. The study is continuing in 2017 with 30 participants. In addition to the knowledge tests, after each laboratory session the students were asked for their opinion in an online survey. A similar percentage of the students stated the execution of the experiments is beneficial for their future professional life. In the hands-on learning mode more students expressed they have acquired new knowledge. Although more students assessed the simulated laboratories as more challenging compared to hands-on experiments, more students mentioned obstacles while conducting the hands-on equivalents.

Conference Key Areas: Open and Online Engineering Education, Engineering Education Research, Sustainability and Engineering Education

Keywords: Hands-on experiment, Simulated experiment, Battery experiment, Learning-modes comparison

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INTRODUCTION

It has been shown that hands-on student laboratory work can significantly influence the outcomes of student learning [1]. Nevertheless, many universities and vocational training institutions conduct laboratories as simulated experiments instead [2]. This is due to the costs of proper laboratory equipment to engage students in effective learning. Another reason is the increased amount of supervision to conduct hands-on labs safely, especially when the object of the experiment is potentially dangerous, such as lithium-ion battery cells [3].

1 RATIONALE

Numerous studies have presented mixed opinions on whether hands-on laboratory work is more conducive to learning than the simulated laboratory [4, 5, 6].

Reflecting on the results of such studies, Ma and Nickerson concluded that many studies did not allow the researchers to reach definite conclusions [2].

Making clear conclusion on learning effectiveness of different modes of laboratory exercises is hampered by design of the abovementioned studies. For example, students conduct hands-on experiments in groups whilst on campus, but are engaged in simulated exercises over the web and individually [6]. As the learning mode is mixed with other influences (in this case supervision, cooperative learning effects, distance learning, instructional papers, synchronicity, etc.), such research compares the combination of all aspects and is unable to specifically identify the difference in learning effectiveness of hands-on and simulated experiments.

The present study compares learning outcomes of student laboratory work conducted in two different modes: first as a practical hands-on exercise and second using computer-based simulations. In order to provide more reliable insights, this study optimized research methodology to avoid other effects on the learning outcome during laboratory work. The student experiments were strictly designed in such a way that the content and procedure were identical in each mode.

2 APPROACH

Each group was taught the same four content areas related to lithium-ion battery cells: two as practical hands-on experiments and two as computer-based simulations. The first group completed the even laboratory sessions as hands-on experiments and the odd ones as computer-based simulations. Planned as a cross-over study, the second group of students were taught the same topics by means of the opposite learning mode. To evaluate the influence of the mode on student learning, short tests on knowledge gained during the previous experiment were conducted at the beginning of the following laboratory session. The mean group results were compared, to answer the question: which mode has been more successful? Additionally, the students were asked for their opinions on each laboratory session in an online survey.

2.1 Learning objectives of the laboratory

Electrochemical cells are a wide and rapidly evolving field. It was therefore decided to limit the new laboratory to teach the most relevant transferable skills and knowledge that are beneficial for the students' future careers. First, they should strengthen their understanding of the characteristic behaviour of battery cells. Second, there is a focus on gaining practical knowledge of the most important parameters of cells and how to determine these parameters self-sufficiently by means of appropriate experimental

setups. With these competencies students are enabled to design experiments with energy storage systems.

The identified learning objectives were grouped to four main content areas: (A) contact and isolation resistance, (B) open-circuit voltage, (C) internal resistance and power, and (D) energy of cells. Grouped in these areas, seven laboratory experiments were designed in such a way that they could be conducted in both modes in the same manner:

- Low Resistance Measurements (A1): Students discover that a multimeter is an inaccurate tool for low ohmic measurements, in the m Ω range, and why such measurement is a misuse of the multimeter. They learn how to use alternative procedures for low ohmic measurements, including a four-wire measurement in AC and DC.
- Contact Resistance (A2): Students conduct experiments with a variety of contact resistance values of typical electrical connections in battery systems.
- Isolation Resistance (A3): Students learn to estimate the influence of moisture on the isolation resistance.
- Open Circuit Voltage Curve (B): Students investigate the dependency of the open circuit voltage of a cell on the state of charge. They use two different types of lithium-ion cells.
- Internal Resistance (C1): Students learn to use AC- and DC- methods to measure internal resistances, being aware of the temperature dependency of battery cells. Students learn to approximate temperature changes caused by a power loss inside a cell.
- Power (C2): Students investigate the maximum discharge rate of battery cells. Students discover the dependency of maximum discharge power from state of charge, pulse duration, and temperature.
- Energy and Capacity (D): Students determine the capacity of a lithium-ion cell and learn about the factors influencing it. They learn to calculate the energy efficiency of both charge and discharge cycles.

Instructions affect the learning outcome of an experiment, e.g. the guidance level can strongly influence student exploration [7]. Thus, for each experiment only a single set of instructions was created and then used in both laboratory modes.

2.2 Creating two comparable groups for the cross-over study

Over the last two years, students enrolled in the energy storages course, were split into two comparable groups based on their prior practical experience to ensure a similar group environment for the individual students.

Forty students were enrolled in the laboratory subject in summer-semester 2016. Thirty students were enrolled in summer-semester 2017. The full semester group in the study program "Electrical Engineering and Electric Mobility" at Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt (THI) is participating in the mandatory laboratory. All students were asked to join the study.

To conduct this educational research as a cross-over study, it was essential to separate the enrolled students into two comparable groups. In this type of study, differences of the compared groups' average performances are detected and equalized by statistics. With the goal of isolating the learning mode in the experiment, we have to consider the in-group interaction in laboratories. Webb found that the same student may have different experiences in different groups, with consequent effects on his or her learning [8].

It was assumed that students with more practical experience may perform better in laboratories than their peers with a lesser practical background. Therefore, in order to assess the level of students' practical experience a preliminary questionnaire was developed. Each year, after analysis of the student responses, students were assigned to two laboratory groups to ensure a similar mix of students with practical experience in each group. [9]

Each student created a code-word that could be used to identify the same individual, while keeping all participants anonymous. Later two lists with code-words were publicized to inform the students which group they were assigned for the laboratory sessions.

2.3 Conducting laboratories in content areas A to D

Each group completed experiments in the four main content areas, two as practical hands-on experiments and two as computer-based simulations. The first group completed the even experiments as hands-on experiments and the odd ones as computer-based simulations. Planned as cross-over study, the second group of students were taught the same topics by means of the opposite learning mode.

For the content area A in simulation-mode, a newly created simulation-website was used. For areas B to D a black box simulation of the hands-on equipment [10] and the battery cell was used. To minimize influences from the user interface to control the experiments, the simulation was accessed through the same graphical user interface as the real hands-on devices. The simulation model emulates all observed effects of the real battery cell and the hands-on devices. The cell simulation model was parametrized to match the outcome of the hands-on experiments.

Each group was split into smaller learning groups of three to five students. The laboratory groups and the learning groups remained unchanged to limit any effects on the result caused by changing cooperative learning.

The students worked autonomously in a supervised environment. All groups were asked to prepare a written laboratory report for each content area before the following session.

2.4 Online survey after conducting the experiments

The students were asked for their thoughts on each laboratory session in a short and fully anonymous online survey. This survey is conducted in both laboratories of the department (chemistry and energy storages) to improve the laboratories. Adequate questions were evaluated to compare the learning modes:

(1) "By conducting the experiment I gained new insights today." (Original: "Ich habe heute durch den Versuch neue Erkenntnisse gewonnen.") This was a yes/no answer and coded 1 or 0.

(2) "At which point in the experiment did you have the biggest problem proceeding with the experiment?" (Original: „An welcher Stelle im Versuch hatten Sie am meisten Probleme voranzukommen?“) This was a free text question which was not compulsory. For data evaluation, the information was coded to 1 if any problem was mentioned or to 0 if students wrote nothing or were expressing they had no problems.

(3) "The procedure of the experiment is quite difficult (1) / feasible (0.5) / easy (0)" (Original: „Die Versuchsdurchführung ist recht schwer (1) / machbar (0.5) / leicht (0)“) The answers were coded in a three step Likert scale.

(4) "The content of the experiment is also relevant for me outside the university; I can imagine that it will be beneficial for my future professional life." (Original: „Der Inhalt des Versuchs hat auch außerhalb der TH Relevanz für mich; ich kann mir vorstellen, im Berufsleben Gewinn aus dieser Versuchsdurchführung zu ziehen.“) The answers were coded in a five step Likert scale: fully agree (1) / somewhat agree (0.75) / maybe (0.50) / somewhat disagree (0.25) / disagree (0)

2.5 Testing the learning outcome

To evaluate the influence of the mode on the student learning, written tests on knowledge gained during the previous experiment were conducted at the beginning of the next laboratory session.

These tests lasted ten minutes and contained a mix of descriptive and multiple choice questions, free answers, and drawings. A positive point system (similar to tests for giving a mark) was used to evaluate the results.

The tests were conducted anonymously. Students were coded through the same self-created code-word used in the questionnaire for grouping.

A priority while planning both semesters was to keep time gaps between experiment and the corresponding test equal for both groups. For organizational reasons, this was not possible at the first content area A in 2016 [9]. In 2017 the laboratories are on the same weekday morning and afternoon, making it easier to keep the experiment – test time gaps equal for both groups.

For the tests, the goal was to always use the computer lab to provide the same environment sitting at a desk while completing the tests. The tests were evaluated and rated using a point system. The average group results between the hands-on and simulated modes were compared, to answer the question: which mode was more successful to transfer the knowledge of the experiment?

3 FINDINGS

3.1 Learning outcome (ten minute tests)

The second run of the experiment is conducted with 30 students in summer semester 2017. In year 2016 with 40 students the range of individual scores was from 12% to 85% for hands-on, and from 12% to 88% for the simulated mode. The distribution of all results was normal. As seen in *Table 1*, for three content areas (A to C) a weak effect towards benefits of the hands-on mode was measured. There was a slight trend demonstrating hands-on laboratory sessions led to a better knowledge acquisition compared to simulated experiments. Content area D showed no difference between the modes. [9]

Overall learning results of hands-on experiments were slightly better than those of simulated laboratories (weak effect, Cohen's $d = 0.22$), but the difference in performance was not statistically significant ($p=0.215 > 0.05$). [9]

3.2 Student feedback

The student feedback results are based on all results of the first iteration and the results of content area A of the current ongoing laboratory in 2017.

(1) In hands-on mode more students expressed they gained new insights (81% vs. 55%, Cohen's $d = 0.56$, medium effect). Pearson's correlation between mode and new insights was 0.28 and significant ($p=0.005$).

(2) A similarly large share of the students mentioned problems while conducting the hands-on experiments or their simulation equivalents (42% hands-on vs. 43% in simulation); Cohen's $d = -0.02$ is showing that there was no effect.

(3) The engagement in the simulated experiments was stated to be a small amount (8% of scale) more difficult (0.38 hands-on vs. 0.46 simulation). Cohen's $d = -0.33$ demonstrates a weak effect.

Table 1. Results of 2016 [9], Effect hands-on vs. simulated

Content Area	Sample Size	Percentage of points Mean Value hands-on	Percentage of points Mean Value simulated	Percentage of points Std. Deviation both modes	Effect size (Cohen's d) "hands-on led to better learning outcome"
A	37	38%	33%	16%	0.28
B	39	54%	49%	16%	0.32
C	35	52%	47%	18%	0.30
D	37	45%	45%	15%	0.04
all	148	47%	44%	17%	0.22

(4) Students who conducted the experiments in the hands-on mode rated the execution of the experiments a little more beneficial for their future professional life (0.58 hands-on vs. 0.55 simulation, Cohen's $d = 0.19$, very weak effect).

No significant correlations between these items were found except between (1) and (4), where Pearson's correlation was 0.41 ($p < 0.001$) and Spearman's rho was 0.38. Looking at both modes separately, the correlation in the simulation mode was stronger (Pearson's $r = 0.52$, $p < 0,001$; Spearman's rho 0.52; $N=49$) compared to the hands-on mode (Pearson's $r = 0.23$, $p=0,115$; Spearman's rho 0.14; $N=48$).

Due to a low response rate for this questionnaire (31%) in the first year (2016), in the second year (2017) the students were recompensed for their time to fill out a questionnaire. Additional 5% of points were added to the grading of the laboratory protocol, which makes it easier to reach the minimum level to pass the subject. In experiment A, which had already been conducted at the writing of this publication, the return rate increased to 77%.

4 CONCLUSIONS

4.1 Learning outcome

This study showed that the described methodology is applicable to focus on the comparison of two learning modes. By excluding many other influences on the comparison of the learning outcome, the results show only a small difference. The slightly better learning results of the hands-on mode are not significant. Some of the excluded factors might have greater impact on student learning than estimated previously. To get statistically significant results more data collection is necessary. This study is going on through 2018 at THI and the methodology will be tested at more universities with different types of students (e.g. international students, summer schools).

4.2 Online survey

The contrast between both modes in the student's subjective opinion about gained knowledge (1) is much more significant than in the objective results of the ten minute tests. The students' opinions show advantages of the hands-on mode: although one cannot determine the students understood more in this mode, one can conclude they gain more confidence in performing similar tasks. In a limited capacity, self-confidence can be considered beneficial for the students' further development by increasing their intrinsic motivation.

The correlation between (1) and (4) shows that students who claimed that they gained new insights also tend to believe that the execution of the experiment will help them in their future professional life. The weaker correlation between (1) and (4) in the hands-on mode suggests that even when the students think they gained additional insights, the students do not consider all of the insights relevant for their profession. Identifying these insights may be beneficial for the improvement of the experiments. Therefore, future surveys will ask for the most beneficial insights gained and whether they consider them useful for their future work outside the university.

Regardless of the learning mode, more than forty percent of the students think they do not benefit in their professional life (4) from the experiments. This is quite disappointing and leads to the possibility of asking for missing content students estimate as important for their future profession.

On one hand less students mention problems with the hands-on experiments (2), while on the other hand they feel the simulated variants to be more difficult (3). When taking a deeper look at the answers from the students, it becomes clear that these results are not correlated. A common mentioned problem was the lack of available measurement devices. Also problems tied to the use of the software could be considered as neutral, as the same software was used in both modes. The difference between the described levels of difficulty of the learning modes (3) raises the question for these reasons. At the time of writing we do not have a final conclusion on this weak effect. For the future evaluation of the study we will ask the students to describe the difficulty in a free text answer.

The actual methodology does not allow one to find correlations between individual learning outcome and student's feedback, as the standard online feedback form is not asking for the self-created code-word that was used in the tests. We plan to implement the new questions and this missing information to a new questionnaire in paper form and use it for the next iteration.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Magin, D. J., Churches, A. E., and Reizes, J. A. (1986), Design and experimentation in undergraduate mechanical engineering, Proc. of the Conference on Teaching Engineering Designers, Institution of Engineers, Sydney, pp. 96-100.
- [2] Ma, J., & Nickerson J. V. (2006), Hands-On, Simulated, and Remote Laboratories: A Comparative Literature Review, *ACM Computing Surveys*, Vol. 38, No 3, Article 7
- [3] Dahn, Jeff and Ehrlich, Grant M. (2011), Lithium-Ion Batteries, *Linden's Handbook of Batteries 4th Edition*, McGraw-Hill, Town, pp. 26.1-26.79.
- [4] Engum, S. A., Jeffries, P., & Fisher, L. (2003), Intravenous catheter training system: Computer-Based education versus traditional learning methods. *American J. Surgery* 186, 1, pp. 67-74.
- [5] McAteer, E., Neil, D., Barr, N., Brown M., Draper, S., & Henderson, F. (1996), Simulation software in a life sciences practical laboratory. *Computers and Education* 26, 1-3, pp. 102-112.
- [6] Edward, N. S. (1996). Evaluation of computer based laboratory simulation. *Computers and Education* 26, 1-3, pp. 123-130.
- [7] Chamberlain, J. M., Lancaster, K., Parson, R. & Perkins K.K., (2014), How guidance affects student engagement with an interactive simulation. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice* 15, p. 628.
- [8] Webb, N. M. (1989), Peer interaction and learning in small groups. *International Journal of Educational Research*, Volume 13, Issue 1, p. 21-39
- [9] F. Steger, A. Nitsche, H.-G. Schweiger and I. Belski, Teaching Battery Basics in Laboratories: Comparing Learning Outcomes of Hands-on Experiments and Computer-based Simulations, Proc. of the 27th Australasian Association for Engineering Education (AAEE) Annual Conference, Coffs Harbour, 2016.
- [10] F. Steger, A. Nitsche, H.-G. Schweiger and I. Belski, Teaching Energy Storages by means of a Student Battery Cell Test System, Proc. of the 45th European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI) Annual Conference, Angra do Heroísmo, 2017.